

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED INDENES

BY K. L. PATHAK AND B. PATHAK

β -Nitrostyrenes have been condensed with acetoacetic ester as well as with acetylacetone. The resultant products on cyclisation have yielded substituted indenenes.

It appears that the Michael condensation on β -nitrostyrenes has not been studied much (Kohler and Engelbrecht, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 764). Condensations of β -nitrostyrene and 3:4-dimethoxy- β -nitrostyrene with ethyl acetoacetate as well as with acetylacetone have been effected in presence of sodium ethoxide in ethanol to form compounds (I) and (II) respectively. It has been observed that even 1:20 molar proportion of sodium ethoxide is quite sufficient to effect condensation in some cases. Duration of reaction markedly affects the yield of the desired product. With increase in temperature of condensation or with increase in time of reaction, side products predominate and the resultant products are tarry, noncrystallisable mass.

The above ketones have been cyclised easily in presence of concentrated H_2SO_4 or a mixture of H_3PO_4 and H_2SO_4 to form indenenes. Such indenenes possessing a nitromethyl group cannot be otherwise prepared easily.

* EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl α -(2-Phenylnitroethyl)acetoacetate (I: X=H).—To a mixture of β -nitrostyrene (30 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (30 g.) in ethanol (125 c.c.), cooled to 5° , was added dropwise with stirring a solution of NaOEt (0.2 g. Na in 10 c.c. ethanol) under cooling. The temperature immediately began to rise, which was controlled at $5-10^\circ$. After the addition was over (20 minutes), white crystals began to separate from the clear solution. Stirring was continued for another 25 minutes and the thick mass was poured into ice-water (800 g.) containing acetic acid (15 c.c.). The separated solid was filtered, washed with water, and subsequently washed with ice-cold ethanol (75 c.c.). The residual solid was dried in air. It was crystallised from petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) in fine, colorless needles, m.p. $76-78^\circ$, yield 45 g. (Found: C, 60.2; H, 6.1; N, 4.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_5N$ requires C, 60.4; H, 5.8; N, 5.03%). It is highly soluble in ethanol and does not exhibit any characteristic colour with $FeCl_3$.

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

1-Nitromethyl-2-carboxy-3-methylindene.—The above crude keto-ester (15 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc., 120 c.c.) at 10-15° and kept at 20-22° for 3 hours. The mass was then poured on ice, the precipitated solid filtered, and washed with water. The crude mass was then dissolved in cold dilute NH_3 , charcoaled, filtered, and acidified with HCl to liberate the acid; yield 40 g. It was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 188°. (Found: C, 61.7; H, 5.1; N, 5.8. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 61.8; H, 4.7; N, 6.0%). On oxidation with alkaline $KMnO_4$ it yielded phthalic acid.

It was esterified with ethanol and dry HCl gas. The ester crystallised from ethanol in light yellow cubes, m.p. 85°. (Found: C, 64.4; H, 5.8; N, 5.49. $C_{14}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 64.36; H, 5.78; N, 5.37%).

Ethyl α -[2-(3': 4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)-nitroethyl]-acetoacetate (I: X=OMe-3': 4').—A mixture of 3: 4-dimethoxy- β -nitrostyrene (10.5 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (7.5 g.) in ethanol (200 c.c.) was treated with NaOEt (0.1 g. Na in 10 c.c. ethanol) in the preceding manner; yield 12 g. It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless needles, m.p. 105-106°. (Found: C, 56.2; H, 5.88. $C_{18}H_{21}O_7N$ requires C, 56.6; H, 6.19%).

1-Nitromethyl-2-ethoxycarbonyl-3-methyl-5: 6-dimethoxyindene.—The above keto-ester (9 g.) was cyclised in a mixture of H_2SO_4 (conc., 30 c.c.) and H_3PO_4 (60 c.c.). The reaction product was an ester and not an acid in this case. It was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 149-50°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 59.6; H, 5.8. $C_{16}H_{19}O_6N$ requires C, 59.81; H, 5.91%).

α -[2-(Phenylnitroethyl)-acetylacetone (II: X=H).—A mixture of β -nitrostyrene (7.5 g.) and acetylacetone (5.5 g.) in ethanol (30 c.c.) was condensed in presence of NaOEt (from 0.1 g. Na) at 5-10°. It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 112-13°, yield 11 g. (Found: C, 62.9; H, 5.85; N, 5.76. $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N$ requires C, 62.65; H, 6.02; N, 5.62%).

1-Nitromethyl-2-acetyl-3-methylindene.—The above compound was cyclised in H_2SO_4 (conc.). It was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow needles, m.p. 103-104°. (Found: C, 67.42; H, 5.67; N, 6.16. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3N$ requires C, 67.53; H, 5.62; N, 6.06%).

α -[2-(3': 4'-Dimethoxyphenyl)nitroethyl]-acetylacetone (II: X=OMe-3': 4').—3: 4-Dimethoxy- β -nitrostyrene (5 g.) was condensed with acetylacetone (2.5 g.) in ethanol (80 c.c.) in presence of NaOEt (out of 0.2 g. Na). It was crystallised from a large volume of ethanol in needles, m.p. 184-86°. (Found: C, 57.84; H, 6.11. $C_{15}H_{19}O_6N$ requires C, 58.25; H, 6.14%).

1-Nitroethyl-2-acetyl-3-methyl-5: 6-dimethoxyindene.—The above compound was cyclised in H_2SO_4 (conc.). It was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 135-37°. (Found: C, 61.5; H, 5.88. $C_{15}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 61.85; H, 5.84%).

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